

An economic analysis of paddy straw burning in Haryana & Punjab

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Abstract

Burning of paddy and wheat straw is creating damage to not only environment but also to farm fertility of the soil as well as its organic quality. The straw has a lot of economic value as livestock fodder and for other uses. Unfortunately the farmers of Punjab and Haryana are not collecting the straw but burning it in the fields. This study aims at understanding of market mechanism of the straw in these states. In last four decade ,the changing demand and supply aspect of paddy and wheat is in opposite direction. Supply of the straw is consistently increasing but demand is stagnant or declining. The demand for the straw in these states is mainly as fodder of large animal such as cattle and buffaloes . Interestingly it is seen that amount of straw as fodder has increased multiple times since 1970-71 but the animals who consume it are declining. Price mechanism has crushed to zero or negative due to the abundance of straw but lesser demand. It is advised to policy makers or government to tackle the straw-burning problem through increasing demand or decreasing supply technique for straw to make it economically viable in market mechanism. This analysis is the basic understanding of economic factors that leads to the problems of residue burning. It will help to design a plan and policy to control the straw burning which is necessary to reduce pollution and sustainable economic development of the states.

Keywords- Paddy Straw Burning Cattle Demand Supply

Introduction

Farmers in Haryana and Punjab set paddy stubble on fire each year around month of October and November to prepare the ground for the next crop. This burning degrades the quality of the soil and causes heavy pollution, but the farmers claim that they

have no other alternative. In Haryana and Punjab, the biomass burning of agricultural field residues (stalks and stubble) during the wheat and rice harvest periods is a significant source of atmospheric pollution in this area (Venkataraman et al., 2006). The University of Agriculture of Punjab (PAU), Ludhiana, reported that total crop residues (paddy and wheat) contained 6 million tonnes of carbon that could produce 22 million tonnes of carbon dioxide during combustion. Open residue fire in the fields destroys vegetation and micro flora and fauna and eliminates a substantial portion of the organic material, thus depleting the organic matter in the fields. According to the findings reported in the Journal of Geophysical Research 2014, due to paddy straw burning, smoke-laden air masses emanating from Haryana filled almost the entire area with a thick layer of airborne particles up to 2.5 kilometers in height. The results revealed more than seven times increase in agricultural fires over Punjab and Haryana during in the peak burning period (mid October to mid November) compared to other states, implying that paddy crop straw burning is much more normal in this region.

What factors are explained in the field burning of crop residues in Haryana and Punjab?

In this paper, I discuss this problem in the light of paddy and wheat residues, an extremely urgent matter, given the understanding of why farmers burn paddy residues, which is crucial for the prescribing of policy reforms. I therefore hope to make a contribution to the prevention policies to reduce the burning of residues in this region.

Objectives of the study

1. To estimate the supply of Rice and wheat straw production in Punjab and Haryana.
2. To assess the present demand aspect of rice straw in the region.

Methodology

To measure total volume of paddy and wheat straw, we are taking the help of straw-to-crop ratio. Straw-to-Crop ratio (SCR) shows that how many kilograms straw is generated to produce one kilogram grain. However, different crops have different straw to crops ratio. According to agricultural scientist, In Punjab and Haryana paddy's Straw to Crop Ratio lies

between 1.8 to 3.5. It varies in different varieties of paddy. Wheat crops' Straw to Crop Ratio is between 1.2 to 2.2. For simplification we are taking 2 as average paddy SCR and 1.5 for wheat.

The paddy and wheat straw is mainly used for animal feeder. however many other use also. To estimate the demand we will check the growth of cattle in both the states. In this paper, statistical abstracts of both states are used.

Rice and Wheat residue and its growth

The total straw quantity in Haryana and Punjab can be shown in the tables below. The source of data of wheat and paddy production in Haryana and Punjab is taken from different statistical abstract of Punjab government and Haryana government.

Table 1: Paddy and wheat straw generation in Haryana

year	Paddy straw (in lakh Tons)	Wheat straw (in lakh Tons)	Total Wheat and Paddy straw (in lakh Tons)	Index of Total base period 1971-72
1971-72	10.7	36.0	46.8	100
1991-92	36.2	97.5	133.8	286
2011-12	75.2	190.3	265.5	567

Source:- Various Statistical Abstracts Of Punjab, Haryana

Table 2: Paddy and wheat straw production in Punjab

year	Paddy straw (in lakh Tons)	Wheat straw (in lakh Tons)	Total Wheat and Paddy straw (in lakh Tons)	Index of Total base period 1971-72
1971-72	18.4	84.3	102.7	100
1991-92	135.1	184.4	319.5	311
2011-12	210.8	259.2	470.0	458

Source:- Various Statistical Abstracts Of Punjab, Haryana

Table 3: Paddy and Wheat straw production in Punjab and Haryana

year	Paddy straw (in lakh Tons)	Wheat straw (in lakh Tons)	Total Wheat and Paddy straw (in lakh Tons)	Index of Total base period 1971-72
1971-72	29.1	120.3	149.4	100
1991-92	171.3	282.0	453.3	303
2011-12	286.0	449.5	735.5	492

Source:- Various Statistical Abstracts Of Punjab, Haryana

The following three tables explain that both wheat and paddy straw has expanded very speedily after green revolution. Table 1 shows that In Haryana total straw from wheat and paddy crops has increased from 46.8 lakh tons to 265.5 lakh tons . It is approximately six times increment in straw availability. Paddy straw has more growth rate than wheat straw in Haryana. Table 2 shows the straw production of wheat and paddy in Punjab after green revolution. The total straw from wheat and paddy was 102.7 lakh Tons in 1971-72 which has increased to 470 lakh tons in 2011-12. In Punjab paddy straw has increased 11 times where as wheat straw has increased 3 times from 1971-72 to 2011-12. So, both Haryana and Punjab have a very high growth rate of straw generation. Table 3 explain the full volume of straw of both crops and of both states. In Haryana and Punjab total straw from wheat and paddy has net increment of 586.1 lakh tons. Paddy straw in both states is 286 lakh tons in 2011-12. Total straw of both states has increased about about five time since 1971-72 to 2011-12.

Demand for paddy straw

Today, Paddy straw is demanded for conventional as well as for modern use.

Demand for “traditional use” of paddy straw is as below:-

1. Fodder for Cattle - Paddy straw has been fed to cattle and buffaloes in India since ages. Although, according to some expert, paddy straw called 'Parali' and wheat straw called 'Turi' on average have similar nutritional values. But in some parts of the country, such as Punjab, Haryana and Western Uttar Pradesh, wheat straw is preferred over paddy straw.Amount of

wheat straw has increased in Punjab and Haryana. There is no scarcity of wheat fodder in the both states. It is also an interesting fact that livestock in Punjab and Haryana is almost stagnant or decreasing since last few years (see the appendix table of livestock census of Punjab and Haryana). So there is no increment in the demand for the fodder in Punjab as well in Haryana. Paddy straw demand has declined due to availability of wheat fodder. Table 4 explains that number of cattle has decreased and number of buffaloes has increased in last four decades, but overall number has a little growth, that is, about eighteen percent in last forty year. The story of Punjab states that in respect to number of cattle, number of buffaloes is more which is shown in the Table 5 It clearly indicates that total bovine has declined more than thirty percent in last forty year. This is the main reason due to which demand for straw as bovine fodder has declined. In both states total bovine has decreased to eight percent in last four decades. Table 6 presents the picture of cattle and buffaloes growth in last forty year span.

Table 1: Cattle and Buffaloes Population In Haryana in Lakh

Year	Cattle	Buffaloes	Total (Cattle and Buffaloes)	Index of Total (base period 1971-72)
1972	24.51	25.18	49.69	100.0
1992	21.3	43.7	65	131.8
2012	18.1	60.9	79	118.1

Source:- Various Statistical Abstracts Of Punjab, Haryana

Table 2: Cattle and Buffaloes Population In Punjab in Lakh

Year	Cattle	Buffaloes	Total (Cattle and Buffaloes)	Index of Total (base period 1971-72)
1972	33.9	37.95	71.85	100.0
1992	23.1	57.6	80.7	100.5
2012	24.3	51.6	75.9	69.2

Source:- Various Statistical Abstracts Of Punjab, Haryana

Table 3: Cattle and Buffaloes Population In Punjab and Haryana (in Lakh)

Year	Cattle	Buffaloes	Total (Cattle and Buffaloes)	Index of Total base period 1971-72
1972	55.2	81.65	136.85	100.0
1992	47.1	105.8	152.9	111.7
2012	48.81	76.78	125.59	91.8

Source:- Various Statistical Abstracts Of Punjab, Haryana

2. Manuring and Composting- This can be done in various ways. Either the stubble is mixed with the soil to maintain soil fertility, a common practice in the rice-growing regions of the country, or, unused and spoiled straw (either left by animals, spoiled during storage or waterlogged and unsuitable for consumption) is generally kept in place along with dung and allowed to form compost, which is then used in manure fields.
3. Thatching- Rice straw is used for thatching in the villages in rice-growing areas, particularly in the Eastern Indian States.
4. Poultry Litter- Chaffed rice straw is used as bedding material in deep litter poultry farms in the Eastern Indian states.
5. Mushroom Cultivation- Straw is used for growth of mushroom culture.
6. Packing Material- Rice straw either chaffed or unchaffed is used as packing material for transport of goods, to avoid breakage/spoilage for glass and crockery items.
7. Industrial Uses- It is industrially used to manufacture paper, straw-board, alcohol, hats and mats, etc.

New use of paddy straw in Punjab and Haryana.

1. Biomass based power generation- In Punjab Approximately 0.48 million tonnes of paddy straw (of the total biomass of 0.93 million tonnes used) are currently being used in 7 biomass power plants to generate 62.5 MW of state power. The Punjab Energy Development Agency aims to use 4.5 million tonnes of paddy straw (of a total of 7.62 million tonnes of biomass used) in 50 plants generating 509.5 MW by 2016-2017. The state government promotes such biomass-based power plants through a variety of incentives. The

Haryana government is also following the same path as the Punjab government.

2. Paper/board/panel making.
3. Briquette making for use in brick kilns and furnaces.
4. Producing bio-ethanol/alcohol/bio gas.

But total demand for paddy straw in Punjab and Haryana is far below the supply of paddy straw. Many traditional uses of paddy straw are declining day by day. This makes paddy straw uneconomic. According to White paper on Management and Utilisation of Paddy Straw in Punjab (Earn, Don't Burn Initiative) by Department of Science, Technology & Environment, Government of Punjab, almost 90 percent paddy straw is burnt by farmers of Punjab. It means in Haryana and Punjab approximately 270 lakh tons (90 percent of 306 lakh tons) was burnt by farmers in 2013-14. It leads to environment and economic loss for whole community. According to Raj Gupta of BISA, "A tonne of rice straw emits three kg of particulate matter, sixty kg of carbon monoxide, 1,460 kg of carbon dioxide, nearly two hundred kg of ash, and two kg of sulphur dioxide. The National Physical Laboratory has estimated that burning sixty three million tonnes of straw in the northern Indian plains releases nearly half a million tonnes of nitrous oxides, close to one lakh tonnes of particulate matter, 3.4 million tonnes of carbon monoxide and greenhouse gases equivalent to 4.8 million tonnes of carbon dioxide". Raj Gupta also stated that due to straw paddy, fields lose nutrients when crop waste is continuously burned in them. Every hectare is filled with 8 kg of nitrogen, 1 kg of phosphorus, 20 kg of potassium, 1 kg of sulphur and 4 kg of calcium. The population of microbes declines. The soil becomes loose and prone to soil erosion.

Before we make any policy to control paddy straw burning in Punjab and Haryana, we should know why burning of paddy straw is the only reason left with farmers rather than selling it.

Basic Factors that are compelling farmer to burn paddy straw

1. Punjab Sub-Soil Water Preservation Act, 2009- Groundwater extraction for rice cultivation has created a major issue for Punjab. Water levels in the state have dropped precipitously over time. In order to deal with this, the Punjab Protection of

Sub-Soil Water Act of 2009 has been enacted, which prohibits farmers from planting rice in fields before or near the onset of monsoons on June 10 of each year. The law was already enacted in Haryana. Farmers who violate the law are fined with an amount of Rs 10,000 a month per hectare. The two states are also improving their water table. The drawback is that the delay in rice planting results in delayed harvesting, leaving the farmer with little time to prepare the field for the next crop.

2. Mechanization of harvesting:-The primary level study in the three districts of Punjab by Ridhima Gupta(2010) shows that the choice of method of harvesting (manual or combined) has direct implications for the management of crop residues. Manual harvesting of cereal crops makes it possible to retrieve crop by-products as crops are cut near ground level. Combining machines or harvesters, on the other hand, makes it difficult to recover residues because the residues are unevenly spread over the harvested fields. Despite this, 85 per cent of the households surveyed in the Patiala cluster reported use of combined methods. The authors attribute the popularity of combine harvesters to potential cost savings, reduced labor management problems and increased timeliness. Manual harvesting is widespread in Basmati varieties for reasons such as reduced breakage, more prone to lodging (reducing the efficiency of mechanical harvesting), more limited field size and more intensive use of residues.
3. Selling Straw is not profitable for farmers- According to farmers ' opinion, an average one gets about two tonnes of rice straw per acre (0.4 hectares). The combine owner or operator charges an additional Rs 850 per acre for harvesting that leftover portion which is of no use to us. It cannot be even fed to the cattle. Blades of fodder cutter easily get blunt by the thick and sharp straw. In few areas, farmers say that only brick kilns, trader for packaging, and farmer from deficit fodder area buy rice straw, but they are limited. Besides, selling rice straw to them is not profitable. They pay farmers Rs 600-Rs 700 a tonne, which means they get Rs 1,200-Rs 1,400 per acre. Now subtract Rs 850 rental cost of the combine harvester and transportation cost of Rs 300, which

- the farmer bore from the amount. All we get is between Rs 50 and Rs 250. Where is the income?
4. **MANREGA Effect-** Mahatma Gandhi National Rural Employment Guarantee Act. (MGNREGA), the flagship programme of GOI implemented by the Ministry of Rural Development (MORD) since 2005 aimed at improving livelihood security of the rural poor and inclusive growth with a primary objective of ensuring wage employment, at least 100 days in a financial year per household. This job guarantee may also serve other secondary objectives such as: generating productive assets, empowering rural women, reducing rural-urban migration and protecting the environment through better management of natural resources, contributing to sustainable agriculture and rural livelihoods. Many studies have also shown that MGNREGA has had a positive impact on the agriculture and livelihoods of small, marginal and landless households in rural areas. However, one of the serious criticisms of MGNREGA is that it has had a negative impact on agriculture in terms of labour shortages, particularly during the peak season. This is due to the diversion of rural farm labour to MGNREGA's work, as MGNREGA's wage rates are much higher than the prevailing farm wages. The lower labour supply to farm labour is also due to the choice of the worker to work in MGNREGA over other labour, due to its less labour, less control and the availability of other facilities. As a result, agricultural labour has become scarce in parts of Punjab and Haryana. The removal and disposal of the paddy stalk that remains in the field is a labour-intensive process. Since labour is unavailable and the preparation of the field for wheat cultivation is limited, the farmer's options are to invest in expensive and rarely used agricultural implements or to burn residues directly on the field. Of the two, the latter is cheaper and needs less effort.
 5. **Inefficient Diversification Policy-** Sukhpal Singh (2004) explains a number of examples of the challenges of alternatives to wheat and rice. He states that sunflowers became a major oilseed crop in Punjab by the early 1990s, but subsequently declined due to factors such as high water

requirements, lack of quality seed availability and vulnerability to adverse weather conditions. It is also reported in a study of horticulture by Garg and Sharma (1999), which lists all possible production obstacles, namely, high production risk, lack of weed control, high incidence of insects and pests, lack of availability of good quality planting material and problems with seed collection. Certainly, some of these issues are due to a lack of infrastructure to support wheat and rice cultivation. Still, flowers (and many fruits and vegetables) are likely to have more complex and uncertain growing processes, particularly for market sales versus household consumption. The former requiring higher standards of quality. Sidhu, Kumar and Singh (2009) make similar points when considering the cultivation of vegetables. They note the increased perishability and production risks associated with the cultivation of vegetables. A study by Birthal et al. (2006) emphasises that high-value vegetable crops may require high-quality inputs and increased knowledge of production techniques, to be successfully grown. In some cases, more capital may be needed, and in others, labour-intensive precision farming. These may be serious limiting factors for diversification, which tended to be limited to relatively large farmers in Punjab.

Conclusion

The study concludes that paddy straw in Punjab and Haryana has increased to a large extent in the last three decades. But demand for paddy straw is declining for traditional use as feed for animal. Farmers prefer to feed wheat straw to their animal than paddy straw. As supply of wheat straw is adequately available farmer have switched to wheat straw and now paddy straw has no market for producer. This makes paddy straw economically nonviable to collect and store, as, it is a bi-product of paddy and farmer cannot control on generation of it. The sustainable disposable method of paddy straw requires heavy costs. If the government of Punjab and government of Haryana want to stop the residue burning, they have to make an increase the demand or a decrease the generation of paddy straw by appropriate policy and planning so that market mechanism can operate and solve the problem of the straw burning.

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